

“YOSH TADQIQOTCHI” ilmiy elektron jurnali

Vebsayt: <http://2ndsun.uz/index.php/yt>

THE ANALYSES OF MAIN CHARACTER IN CHRISTOPHER MARLOWE’S TRAGEDY “TAMBURLAINE THE GREAT”

Mokhichehra Pulatova Temirovna

Teacher of Pedagogical Institute of Bukhara State University

INFO:

Accepted: 22.03.2022
Reviewed: 24.03.2022
Published: 27.03.2022

Keywords: *play, historical reality, hero, blank verse, cruel genius, tragedy*

ABSTRACT

This article illustrates the analyses of main character in Christopher Marlowe’s tragedy “Tamburlaine the great”.

Copyright © 2022. [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/)

Christopher Marlowe (1564 - 1593) – an English Renaissance poet and dramatist. Although he lived only 29 years, he managed to write valuable masterpieces as “The Jew of Malta”, “Edward the Second”, “The Massacre at Paris”, “Doctor Faustus” and others. Marlowe's first play performed on the regular stage in London, in 1587, was “Tamburlaine the Great”, about the conqueror Tamburlaine, who rises from shepherd to war-lord. It is among the first English tragedies in blank verse. The play was a success, and was followed by “Tamburlaine the Great, Part II”. The two parts of Tamburlaine were published in 1590. The prologue in “Tamburlaine the Great” begins with the following lines:

From jiggling veins of rhyming mother wits,
And such conceits as clownage keeps in pay,
We'll lead you to the stately tent of war,
Where you shall hear the Scythian Tamburlaine
Threat'ning the world with high astounding terms

And scourging kingdoms with his conquering sword.
View but his picture in this tragic glass,
And then applaud his fortunate as you please.

Tamburlaine is depicted as barbarous Scythian who is threatening the world with his sword. In the first part of play Marlowe describes Tamburlaine's appearance and the process of his occupation of other countries by force of arms.

Marlowe's Tamburlaine is a tall, broad shouldered person with long arms and golden hair. Clearly, he looks like Europeans.

In Marlowe's tragedy Tamburlaine is a Scythian shepherd and a nomadic bandit who wants to take revenge upon life for injustice and gathers under his banner poor dissatisfied people like himself. For example:

Theridamas
Tamburlaine! A Scythian shepherd so embellished
With nature's pride and richest furniture!
His looks do menace heaven and dare the gods;
His fiery eyes are fix'd upon the earth,

Here Tamburlaine is described as Scythian shepherd with fiery eyes, who rebels against God and Heaven.

In the play Tamburlaine is described as an ambitious and haughty person. For example, at the end of the work Tamburlaine conquers Babylon, and achieves high peak of power, and considers himself above God, and orders to burn the holy Quran in the fire. With deeds like this Tamburlaine turns God's will against himself. The tragedy of the hero begins here. He feels a sudden weakness, and all his efforts to overcome the disease fail. Here the literary hero's blaspheme of God and the holy books do not coincide with historical reality. As we know, Amir Temur was a religious person. "He knew the Koran by heart and could debate with outstanding religious scholars."

In the next lines Mycetes (king of Persia) is illustrated speaking with his lords about Tamburlaine. One of the Persian lords Meander is complaining about Tamburlaine's deeds and calling him as Scythian thief who robs Persian merchants.

Meander
Oft have I heard your majesty complain
Of Tamburlaine, that sturdy Scythian thief,
That robs your merchants of Persepolis
Trading by land unto the Western Isles...
Hoping, misled by dreaming prophecies,
To reign in Asia, and with barbarous arms
To make himself the monarch of the East.

Meander is disgruntled because barbarous Tamburlaine is conquering the Asia and making himself the monarch of whole East.

Uzbek poet Maruf Jalil, who translated “Tamburlaine the Great” from Russian into Uzbek, states: "Marlowe’s Tamburlaine is not a biographical work, he promotes the idea of romantic works of the period. Tamburlaine is described as unfair, harsh, cruel genius. He is "Wrath of Doom," "Sword of Vengeance" sent by God to punish the rulers who forgot about justice. The author created the image of a powerful genius who never knew defeat."

At the end of the work the author ends up the life of the hero with his death. The disease makes him to stop his conquering deeds and he bequeaths his heirs:

First, take my scourge and my imperial crown,
And mount my royal chariot of estate
That I may see thee crowned before I die.

In this example, the hero of the tragedy Tamburlaine even at the end of his life doesn’t pray to God but orders his heirs to continue the war actions. It doesn’t coincide with the image of Amir Temur who asked his sons to maintain peace.

The aim of the present study was to determine whether an association exists between the duration of menopause and the age of menopause onset, and the differences in bone mineral density (BMD) in postmenopausal women.¹

A special place in the work of Utkir Khashimov is occupied by the novel “Between Two Doors”. The writer is concerned not only with the pressing social issues of today, but with eternal moral problems. In particular, by calling “Between Two Doors”, the writer means the path of person, which he walked from birth to death.²

The article considers the role of the state in ensuring sustainable development of tourism in Uzbekistan. In the conditions of innovative development of the economy, sustainable development of tourism occurs as a result of economic integration and the systematic improvement of international relations. With the innovative development of the economy, the role and prestige of tourism in the national economy is growing. Tourism is one of the most profitable sectors of the economy.³

Today richness of Uzbek terminology is mainly due to the use of other languages and word formation is giving. The main factor that determines the stability of a particular terminological system in a particular field is its regularity.⁴

The communicative method as the ultimate goal of learning involves the formation of communicative competence, which consists of linguistic, speech, subject, socio-cultural, educational and compensatory competencies.⁵

¹ Najmutdinova, D. K., Nurmukhamedova, L. S., Alieva, D. A., Maksudova, D. S., & Nosirova, Z. A. (2016). Study of the effects of the age at menopause and duration of menopause on bone mineral density in postmenopausal women in Uzbekistan. *International Journal of Biomedicine*, 6(1), 38-40.

² Turaeva, K., & Zarinabonu, A. (2022). Interpretation Of Woman Image in Modern Uzbek Literature (Based on Utkir Khashimov’s Book “Between Two Doors”). *Eurasian Research Bulletin*, 4, 42-44.

³ Abdullaeva, A. A., & Kizi, K. D. R. (2020). Role of the state in ensuring sustainable development of tourism. *European science*, (1 (50)).

⁴ Bakhtiyorovna, N. M., & Zoirovna, N. I. Terms and Terminology in the Uzbek and English Languages. *International Journal on Integrated Education*, 3(1), 173-176.

⁵ Абдуллаева, Л. С., Самадова, С. А., & Махмурова, М. (2014). Современные методы преподавания иностранных языков. *Коммуникативный метод. Наука. Мысль: электронный периодический журнал*, (6), 73-76.

The main purpose of teaching computer graphics in school in the article is to teach students the order and rules of computer-aided drawing of graphic information, such as drawings, diagrams and schemes, performed in the disciplines of drawing and engineering graphics.⁶

This article is devoted to the study of Somerset Maugham's short story "The Book Bag". It mainly focuses on the analysis of moral and immoral issues, emphasizing to the matter of incest and its fatal outcomes.⁷

The article considers the correlation of the real facts and imagination in "Tamburlaine the Great" by Christopher Marlowe.⁸

Synonyms are formed from the combination of the Greek words syn" together"+ onoma" name", which is an important means of increasing the effectiveness of speech, a clearer, more vivid, logical and diverse expression of thought.⁹

The nature of the semantic volume of the word, language corpus and creating Uzbek language corpus is under the analysis of this article. This issue of principle importance for semasiological research has been interpreted in different ways in linguistics.¹⁰

This article covers the main place of small business and business in today's market economy. Including scientifically analyzed the development of small business and business, and the legal basis, at this time financially support small business and business, the latter is amended and the rules for this branch of national legislation are added.¹¹

In the national economy, as in the economic systems of a number of foreign countries, the concept of public-private partnership (PPP) is being actively implemented.¹²

This article discusses the socio-philosophical importance of gender equality in today's increasingly globalized world. At the same time, in Uzbekistan, which is developing rapidly in all directions, the current issues of women's legal freedoms, protection of their legitimate interests, social relations of women in society and the development of society, social cohesion, family, traditions, It has been scientifically stated that culture, international and inter-civilizational relations, religion, labor and organization of public organizations are of great importance.¹³

In fact, Marlowe's Tamburlaine has a great difference from real Amir Temur (Tamerlane) but it's wrong to say that the author himself intentionally wanted to exaggerate a real man's life and his actions negatively. The one who reads the work comes to the

⁶ Ruzimurodova, Z., & Mamatov, D. K. (2021). PECULIARITIES OF THE USE OF COMPUTER TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING ENGINEERING GRAPHICS. *World Bulletin of Social Sciences*, 4(11), 136-140.

⁷ Pulatova, S. (2021). SUPERIORITY OF MORAL IDEAS AND FATAL RESULTS OF IMMORALITY IN THE SHORT STORY OF SOMERSET MAUGHAM "THE BOOK BAG". *Збірник наукових праць ЛОГОΣ*.

⁸ Temirovna, M. P. (2021). THE CORRELATION OF HISTORICAL TRUTH AND IMAGINATION IN CHRISTOPHER MARLOWE'S TRAGEDY "TAMBURLAINE THE GREAT". *Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal*, 2(12), 455-457.

⁹ Mirxanova, G. R. (2021). EMERGENCE AND STAGE OF DEVELOPMENT OF FIRST SYNONYM DICTIONARIES. *Scientific reports of Bukhara State University*, 5(2), 96-105.

¹⁰ Bahodirovna, A. D. Semantic Labeling of Language Units. *International Journal on Integrated Education*, 3(1), 177-179.

¹¹ Tolibjonovich, Madumarov T., and Gulomjonov O. R. Ogli. "Lombard Microcredit Organization Its Concept and Its Importance Today." *JournalNX*, vol. 6, no. 10, 2020, pp. 109-111.

¹² Madumarov Talatbek Tolibjonovich, & Gulomjonov Odiljon Rahimjon o'g'li. (2021). PREREQUISITES FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF A LEASING MECHANISM IN PUBLIC - PRIVATE PARTNERSHIP. *International Engineering Journal For Research & Development*, 6(SP), 5. <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/7MXR3>

¹³ Фуломжонов, О. Р. Ў. (2021). ЖАМИЯТ ТАРАҚҚИЁТИНИНГ ЯНГИ БОСҚИЧИДА ГЕНДЕР ТЕНГЛИКНИ ТАЪМИНЛАШНИНГ ИЖТИМОИЙ АҲАМИЯТИ. *Scientific progress*, 1(4).

conclusion that Marlowe wanted to create his hero based on the real life and real historical person. But in the sixteenth century Western Orientalists had wrong information and were not completely aware of real facts on a historical man Amir Temur. And Marlowe created his work based on historical sources of that time. That's why his hero differs from real historical person.

REFERENCE:

1. Najmutdinova, D. K., Nurmukhamedova, L. S., Alieva, D. A., Maksudova, D. S., & Nosirova, Z. A. (2016). Study of the effects of the age at menopause and duration of menopause on bone mineral density in postmenopausal women in Uzbekistan. *International Journal of Biomedicine*, 6(1), 38-40.
2. Turaeva, K., & Zarinabonu, A. (2022). Interpretation Of Woman Image in Modern Uzbek Literature (Based on Utkir Khashimov's Book "Between Two Doors"). *Eurasian Research Bulletin*, 4, 42-44.
3. Abdullaevna, A. A., & Kizi, K. D. R. (2020). Role of the state in ensuring sustainable development of tourism. *European science*, (1 (50)).
4. Bakhtiyorovna, N. M., & Zoirovna, N. I. Terms and Terminology in the Uzbek and English Languages. *International Journal on Integrated Education*, 3(1), 173-176.
5. Абдуллаева, Л. С., Самадова, С. А., & Махмурова, М. (2014). Современные методы преподавания иностранных языков. Коммуникативный метод. Наука. Мысль: электронный периодический журнал, (6), 73-76.
6. Ruzimurodova, Z., & Mamatov, D. K. (2021). PECULIARITIES OF THE USE OF COMPUTER TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING ENGINEERING GRAPHICS. *World Bulletin of Social Sciences*, 4(11), 136-140.
7. Pulatova, S. (2021). SUPERIORITY OF MORAL IDEAS AND FATAL RESULTS OF IMMORALITY IN THE SHORT STORY OF SOMERSET MAUGHAM "THE BOOK BAG". Збірник наукових праць ЛОГОΣ.
8. Temirovna, M. P. (2021). THE CORRELATION OF HISTORICAL TRUTH AND IMAGINATION IN CHRISTOPHER MARLOWE'S TRAGEDY "TAMBURLAINE THE GREAT". *Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal*, 2(12), 455-457.
9. Mirxanova, G. R. (2021). EMERGENCE AND STAGE OF DEVELOPMENT OF FIRST SYNONYM DICTIONARIES. *Scientific reports of Bukhara State University*, 5(2), 96-105.
10. Bahodirovna, A. D. Semantic Labeling of Language Units. *International Journal on Integrated Education*, 3(1), 177-179.
11. Tolibjonovich, Madumarov T., and Gulomjonov O. R. Ogli. "Lombard Microcredit Organization Its Concept and Its Importance Today." *JournalNX*, vol. 6, no. 10, 2020, pp. 109-111.
12. Madumarov Talatbek Tolibjonovich, & Gulomjonov Odiljon Rahimjon o'g'li. (2021). PREREQUISITES FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF A LEASING MECHANISM IN PUBLIC-PRIVATE PARTNERSHIP. *International Engineering Journal For Research & Development*, 6(SP), 5. <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/7MXR3>
13. Фуломжонов, О. Р. Ў. (2021). ЖАМИЯТ ТАРАҚҚИЁТИНИНГ ЯНГИ БОСҚИЧИДА ГЕНДЕР ТЕНГЛИКНИ ТАЪМИНЛАШНИНГ ИЖТИМОЙ АҲАМИЯТИ. *Scientific progress*, 1(4).